

Determination of kinetic parameters from DTA curves

Manabesh Bhattacharya^{a*}, W. G. Devi^b and P. S. Mazumdar^c

^aDepartment of Physics, Krishnath College, Berhampore-742 101, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, T. S. Paul Manipur Women's College, Monsangei, Imphal-795 008, India

^cDepartment of Physics, Acharya Prafulla Chandra College, New Barrackpore-743 276, India

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A method is considered for the determination of the kinetic parameters of a Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) curve. The method utilizes the peak temperature, rising side area and falling side area of a DTA curve. The validity of the method is tested by applying it both to the computer simulated and experimental DTA curves.

Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA) is an indispensable tool for the study of complex chemical reactions. DTA curves are also used for quantitative identification of organic and inorganic compounds. As a result the determination of kinetic parameters associated with a DTA curve, namely, order of kinetics (n), activation energy (E) and pre-exponential factor (A) is an active area of research. In literature there are a number of methods for the determination of kinetic parameters¹⁻⁴. In the present paper we consider a method for the determination of kinetic parameters of a DTA curve. The method uses the peak temperature, rising side area and falling side area of a DTA curve. We adjudge the suitability of the method by applying it both to computer generated and experimental DTA curves.

Theory :

Following Balarin⁵, the expression for the solid state decomposition reaction of n -th order can be expressed as

$$-dx/dt = A \exp(-E/RT) x^n/x_0^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

where x is the concentration of some kind of reactant at time t and x_0 the initial concentration. In a DTA curve the temperature deviations (ΔT) from the horizontal base line can be expressed as⁶

$$\Delta T = -\beta dx/dt \quad (2)$$

where β is the proportionality constant. From eqns. (1) and (2) we get,

$$\Delta T = A \beta \exp(-E/RT) [1 + (n-1) A/\phi \int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT') dT']^{n/(1-n)} \quad \text{for } n \neq 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta T = A \beta \exp(-E/RT) [-A/\phi \int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT') dT'] \quad \text{for } n = 1 \quad (4)$$

where ϕ is the heating rate, T_0 the temperature at time $t = 0$

and T the temperature at time t . At the peak temperature $T = T_m$, the deflection of the DTA curve is maximum so that $[d\Delta T/dT]_{T=T_m} = 0$ (5)

From eqns. (3)–(5) one gets,

$$1 + (n-1) A/\phi \int_{T_0}^{T_m} \exp(-E/RT') dT' = nART_m^2/(\phi E) \exp(-E/RT_m) \quad \text{for } n \neq 1 \quad (6)$$

$$\phi E/(RT_m^2) = \exp(-E/RT_m) \quad \text{for } n = 1 \quad (7)$$

It is shown by Chen and Kirsh⁷ that for a given value of E the integral,

$\int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT') dT'$ is a strongly increasing function of T so that

$$\int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT') dT' = \int_0^T \exp(-E/RT') dT' \quad (8)$$

Now following Devi⁸ we can write,

$$\int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT') dT' = E E_2(u)/Ru \quad (9)$$

with $u = E/RT$ and $E_2(u)$ is the second exponential integral⁹. Using eqns. (3), (4), (6) and (7) we can write,

$$\Delta T/(\Delta T)_m = \exp[u_m - u + F(u, u_m)] \quad \text{for } n = 1 \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta T/(\Delta T)_m = \exp(u_m - u) [1 - (n-1) F(u, u_m)/n]^{n/(1-n)} \quad \text{for } n \neq 1 \quad (11)$$

with

$$F(u, u_m) = u_m^2 \exp(u_m) [E_2(u_m)u_m - E_2(u)/u] \quad (12)$$

$(\Delta T)_m$ is the maximum value of ΔT and $u_m = E/RT_m$.

Following Balarin⁵ one can arrive at the symmetry factor S characterizing the peak,

$$S = x_m/x_0 \quad (13)$$

where x_m is the concentration for $T = T_m$.

From eqn. (2) we get

$$S = A/\phi A \quad (14)$$

where A_f is the area of the falling side of the DTA curve and A the area of the whole DTA curve and they are given by

$$A_f = \int_{T_m}^{T_e} (\Delta T) dT \quad (15)$$

$$A = \int_{T_0}^{T_e} (\Delta T) dT \quad (16)$$

where T_e is the end-point temperature of the peak.

It has been found that S depends on n and u_m . Considering a number of DTA curves and using the technique of least-square non-linear regression^{10,11} we get,

$$\ln(S) = -1.259/(n + 0.592) + 1.52/u_m - 0.2 \quad (17)$$

with

$$A_0 n^2 + A_1 n + A_2 = 0 \quad (18)$$

where

$$A_0 = -0.2 - \ln(A_f/A) \quad (19)$$

$$A_1 = 1.52 A_f/T_m - 0.592 \ln(A_f/A) - 1.378 \quad (20)$$

$$A_2 = 0.9 A_f/A \quad (21)$$

On solving eqn. (18) we get two roots. The smaller root lies between 0.7 and 2.5, which is the range of values of the order of kinetics (n) considered. The other root being spurious is thereby neglected and the smaller root corresponds to n . On the other hand it is found that to a good approximation by using technique of standard linear and non-linear regression^{11,12},

$$E = (1.124 + 1.427 n - 0.113 n^2) RT_m^2 / (T_{0.5}^+ - T_{0.5}^-) - (0.902 + 0.346 n + 0.61 n^2) RT_m \quad (22)$$

where $T_{0.5}^-$ and $T_{0.5}^+$ are, respectively, the temperatures in the rising and falling sides of the peak corresponding to the points at which $\Delta T/(\Delta T)_m = 1/2$.

Now, knowing E and n , pre-exponential factor can be evaluated from eqns. (6) and (7),

$$A = \phi [nRT_m^2/E \exp(-E/RT_m) - (n-1) \int_{T_0}^{T_m} \exp(-E/RT) dT]^{-1} \quad (23)$$

Results and Discussion

The areas A_f and A have been calculated by sub-dividing the entire range into a number of subranges. Let us consider the evaluation of A ,

$$A = \int_{T_0}^{T_{01}^-} (\Delta T) dT + \int_{T_{01}^-}^{T_{02}^-} (\Delta T) dT + \int_{T_{02}^-}^{T_{03}^-} (\Delta T) dT + \dots + \int_{T_{01}^+}^T (\Delta T) dT \quad (24)$$

The temperatures T_x^\pm for which $\Delta T/(\Delta T)_m = x$, have been evaluated by solving eqns. (10) and (11) by Newton-McAuley method¹³. Eqns. (10) and (11) can be expressed,

respectively, as

$$\alpha = \exp [(u_m - u) + F(u, u_m)] \text{ for } n = 1 \quad (25)$$

$$\alpha = \exp (u_m - u) [1 - (n - 1) F(u, u_m)/n]^{n/(1-n)} \text{ for } n \neq 1 \quad (26)$$

According to Newton-McAuley method¹³,

$$u^{(j+1)} = u^{(j)} - \alpha(u^{(j)}) / (d\alpha/du)_{u=u^{(j)}} \quad (27)$$

where $u^{(j)}$ is the j -th approximation to u . From eqns. (25) and (26) we get,

$$d\alpha/du = \alpha(dF/du - 1) \text{ for } n = 1 \quad (28)$$

and

$$d\alpha/du = -\alpha + dG/du \exp(u_m - u) \text{ for } n \neq 1 \quad (29)$$

with

$$G = D^{-n/(n-1)} \quad (30)$$

$$D = 1 - (n - 1) F(u, u_m)/n \quad (31)$$

$$dG/du = -(dD/du)nG/((n - 1) D) \quad (32)$$

$$dD/du = -(n - 1)(dF/du)/n \quad (33)$$

$$dF/du = (u_m/u)^2 \exp(u_m - u) \quad (34)$$

Using Newton-McAuley method (eqn. (27)), eqns. (25) and (26) have been solved to find out the temperatures T_x^- and T_x^+ for various values of $x = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, \dots$. Now knowing the temperatures T_x^\pm , the integrals in eqn. (24) have been evaluated by using 16-point Gauss-Legendre quadrature⁹. The second exponential integral has been evaluated by following the technique suggested by Devi⁸ in which its continued fraction representation is used¹⁴. For computer simulated curves, T_0 and T_e have been determined by solving eqns. (25) and (26) for $x = 0.001$.

In Table 1 we present the kinetic parameters of some computer simulated DTA peaks as calculated by the present method. E_{in} and E_p denote respectively the input value of the activation energy and the activation energy as calculated by the present method. n_{in} , n_p and A_{in} , A_p are the corresponding values of order of kinetics and pre-exponential fac-

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of some computer simulated DTA peaks

E_{in} kJ mol ⁻¹	n_{in}	A_{in} s ⁻¹	E_p kJ mol ⁻¹	n_p	A_p s ⁻¹
154.30	2.5	1.0 (13)	154.06	2.52	9.48 (12)
154.30	1.9	1.0 (13)	154.69	1.91	1.09 (13)
38.57	1.5	1.0 (13)	38.58	1.50	1.01 (13)
154.30	1.5	1.0 (9)	154.31	1.50	1.00 (9)
38.57	1.5	1.0 (9)	38.57	1.51	1.00 (9)
154.30	0.7	1.0 (5)	155.35	0.69	1.13 (5)
38.57	1.9	1.0 (5)	38.58	1.89	1.00 (5)

tor. It is evident from Table 1 that there is reasonably good agreement between the input values of kinetic parameters and those calculated by the present method. Figs. 1 and 2 we present respectively a computer generated DTA curve and an experimental DTA curve.

Fig. 1. A computer generated DTA curve with $E = 154.30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $n = 1.9$ and $A = 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 2. An experimental DTA curve for the decomposition of calcitic limestone with $\phi = 6^\circ/\text{min}$.

Encouraged by our findings for the case of computer simulated DTA peaks we have applied the present method to determine the kinetic parameters of a number of DTA curves selected from the literature, namely those of calcitic limestone^{15,16}, georgia kaloinite^{15,16}, Eureka halloysite^{15,16}, cyclotrimethylenetrinitrane (RDX)¹⁷ and trinitrotoluene (TNT)¹⁷.

For experimental DTA curves the areas have been found using the cubic spline method¹³. The results are displayed in Table 2. The kinetic parameters as calculated by the present method are in fair agreement with those reported in the literature.

Conclusion : Here we have studied a method of determination of kinetic parameters and applied it to calculate

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of some experimental DTA peaks

System	Φ $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$	E_p kJ mol^{-1}	n_p	A_p s^{-1}
Georgia kaloinite ^a	6	36.41	1.01	3.17 (6)
Eureka halloysite ^a	6	37.66	1.01	4.76 (6)
Calcitic limestone ^a	6	46.78	0.535	7.20 (6)
RDX ^b	6	45.05	0.848	2.34 (17)
RDX ^b	15	46.49	0.959	6.56 (17)
TNT ^b	6	21.96	1.65	6.81 (5)
TNT ^b	10	21.01	1.74	2.89 (5)

^aRefs. 15, 16. ^bRef. 17.

the kinetic parameters of some computer simulated and experimental DTA curves. It may be noted that we have obtained reasonably good results.

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